

New species of *Aspiculuris* (Spirurida, Oxyuroidea: Heteroxynematidae) in *Dolichotis patagonum* (Rodentia: Caviidae) from San Juan Province, Argentina

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Abstract: A new species of *Aspiculuris* (Oxyuroidea: Heteroxynematidae) collected from the cecum of the Patagonian mara *Dolichotis patagonum* in San Juan Province, Argentina, is described. The new species differs from the rest of the species assigned to *Aspiculuris* from the Neotropics (*Aspiculuris tetraptera*, *Aspiculuris mexicana*) and Nearctic (*Aspiculuris huascaensis*, *Aspiculuris americana*) by its large size, the abrupt termination of the cervical alae immediately posterior to the bulb-intestine junction, and its unusual host. *Aspiculuris sanjuanensis* sp. nov. is considerably larger than congeners from the Neotropical or Nearctic regions. It exhibits a cervical ala terminating posterior to the bulb-intestine junction (versus mid-termination oesophageal bulb in *Aspiculuris tetraptera*, *Aspiculuris mexicana* and *Aspiculuris huascaensis*). *Aspiculuris sanjuanensis* sp. nov. represents the third Neotropical species of *Aspiculuris*, the first record for Argentina and the first in a Caviidae rodent.

Keywords: conservation center, mountain region, Neotropics, rodent

Introduction

The genus *Aspiculuris* Schulz, 1927 (Spirurida: Heteroxynematidae) comprises 12 species (Hodda, 2022) reported from the Nearctic, Palaearctic, Ethiopian, and Neotropical regions (Lynggaard et al., 2020). Members of *Aspiculuris* genus segregate into two morphological groups: the more diverse group exhibits cervical alae that terminate abruptly with posterior pointed ends, while a smaller group possesses rounded posterior ala margins (Quentin, 1975; Liu et al., 2012).

Species of *Aspiculuris* are exclusive parasites of rodents of the order Rodentia (Cricetidae, Sciuridae

and Muridae) (Lynggaard et al., 2020), although eggs of *Aspiculuris* have been reported in carnivores *Leopardus guigna* Molina, 1782 and *Lycalopex fulvipes* (Martin, 1837) in South America, more specifically on Chiloé Island, Chile (Acosta-Jamett et al., 2018).

In the Neotropics, two *Aspiculuris* species have been described: *Aspiculuris tetraptera* (Nitzsch, 1821) in Muridae rodents (Hugot, 1980), and *Aspiculuris mexicana* Lynggaard, García-Prieto, Guzmán-Cornejo & Osorio-Sarabia, 2020 in Cricetidae hosts (Lynggaard et al., 2020). To date, no previous records of this genus of nematodes exist for Argentina, despite numerous studies of rodent parasitic nematodes.

Dolichotis patagonum (Zimmermann, 1780) (Rodentia: Caviidae), known as the mara or Patagonian hare, is the most representative endemic mammal and the second-largest rodent of Argentina, after the capybara *Hydrochoerus hydrochaeris* (Linnaeus, 1766). *Dolichotis patagonum* has a distribution in several provinces (Bauni et al., 2021), making it a vulnerable species (Villafañe et al., 2005; Chebez & Nigro, 2008; SAyDS-SAREM, 2019). It is currently present in various provinces of Argentina (Bauni et al., 2021). It is diurnal, herbivorous, and active in morning and late afternoon in winter, nocturnally in summer, feeding on shrubs and grasses (Villafañe et al., 2005; Giannoni et al., 2021).

Herein, we describe a new *Aspiculuris* species parasitising the cecum and colon of *D. patagonum* in San Juan Province, Argentina. This constitutes the third Neotropical *Aspiculuris*, the first documented in Argentina, and the first associated with a Caviidae host.

Materials and methods

In June 2024, an adult female *D. patagonum* obtained from the Wildlife Rehabilitation, Environmental Education, and Responsible Recreation Center located in the department of Rivadavia, San Juan Province, Argentina (Parque Faunístico: 31°30'19.99"S, 68°38'40.45"W) (Fig. 1), was necropsied. The specimen originally came from the town of Mogna, department of Jáchal, San Juan Province. A ventral midline incision exposed the body cavity; the digestive tract was removed and examined under a stereomicroscope. Nematodes were preserved in 70% ethanol and prepared as semi-permanent lactophenol mounts. Identification was carried out using an optical microscope (Arcano Xsp) and followed Hugot (1980), Lynggaard et al. 2020. Specimens are deposited in the Parasitological Collection of the Center (Parque Faunístico): (CRFSJ_P_54A; CRFSJ_P_54B). Drawings were made with a camera lucida.

Ethical aspects

All applicable international, national, and/or institutional guidelines for the care and use of animals were strictly followed. All sample collection protocols complied with current Argentine laws.

Fig. 1. (A) South America; (B) Argentina; (C) San Juan Province; Location of the Wildlife Rehabilitation, Environmental Education, and Responsible Recreation Center (Parque Faunístico) (red triangle); The town of Mogna, Jáchal Department (blue star).

All animal procedures performed in this research were carried out in accordance with the ethical standards of the institution or organisation where the study was conducted.

Results

Seven adult nematodes (five females, two males) were recovered from the cecum of *D. patagonum* (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. *Dolichotis patagonum* from the Wildlife Rehabilitation, Environmental Education, and Responsible Recreation Center (Parque Faunístico). (A) lateral view, (B) frontal view.

Fig. 3. Male of *Aspiculuris sanjuanensis* sp. nov. collected from *D. patagonum*. (A) anterior end, frontal view; (B) posterior end, frontal view, showing papillae distribution; (C and D) posterior end, lateral view, showing papillae. vc = cephalic vesicle, e = oesophagus, ca = caudal ala, nr = nerve ring, b = bulb, i = intestine, 1st, 2nd, and 3rd = caudal alae.

Nematoda Rudolphi, 1808

Order Spirurida

Family Heteroxynematidae Skryabin & Schikhobalova, 1948

Genus *Aspiculuris* Schulz, 1927

Aspiculuris sanjuanensis sp. nov. González-Rivas, Castillo and Simoncelli (Figs 3, 4).

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General description: Medium-sized, white nematodes showing sexual dimorphism; males smaller than females. Both sexes bear cervical alae originating immediately posterior to the cephalic vesicle and terminating abruptly with a sharp posterior angle just behind the oesophageal bulb-intestine junction. Oral opening with three lips, bearing approximately six

prominent structures, surrounded by four large cephalic papillae and two amphids. This oral cavity is followed by the pharynx, oesophagus, a well-developed bulb and long intestine which terminating at an anal opening (females) or cloacal aperture (males). Excretory pore absent in both sexes. Males possess three pairs of caudal alae and 13 caudal papillae: one lateral precloacal pair; two adcloacal pairs around the cloaca; one lateral postcloacal pair; one ventral postcloacal pair; one single ventral papilla; and one distant ventral postcloacal pair.

Male (based on 2 adult specimens) (μm) (Fig. 3): Total body length 6310 ± 64 (6265–6356); maximum width 192 ± 79 (136–249); cephalic vesicle length 19.6 ± 0.07 (19.6–19.7); cephalic vesicle width 9.9 ± 0.1 (9.8–10); cervical alae length 852 ± 0.28 (852–853); oesophageal length 808 ± 7 (803–813); bulb length 251 ± 9 (245–258); bulb width 161 ± 20 (147–

Fig. 4. Female of *Aspiculuris sanjuanensis* sp. nov. collected from *D. patagonum*. (A) anterior end, frontal view; (B) anterior end, frontal view, showing vulva with eggs; (C) egg; (D) anterior end, frontal view, showing vulva with eggs; (E) mid-body, lateral view, showing vulva with eggs. vc = cephalic vesicle, e = oesophagus, ca = caudal ala, nr = nerve ring, b = bulb, i = intestine, v = vulva, eg = egg, a = anus, u = uterus.

176); distance to nerve ring 259 ± 20 (245–274); tail length 97 ± 0.7 (97–98).

Female (based on 3 adult specimens) (μm) (Fig. 4): Total body length 9503 ± 73 (9420–9556); maximum width 393 ± 47 (340–431); cephalic vesicle length 38.6 ± 16 (29–58); cephalic vesicle width 9.8; cervical alae length 965 ± 21 (950–980); oesophageal length 931; bulb length 294; bulb width 215 ± 26 (196–245); distance to nerve ring 538 ± 0.58 (538–539); distance to vulva 5670 ± 5 (5665–5675). Eggs elliptical, 359 ± 74 (294–441) long, 52 ± 11 (40–62) wide.

Taxonomic summary

Type host: Mara or Patagonian hare, *Dolichotis patagonum*.

Type locality: Mogna, Jáchal Department, San Juan Province ($30^{\circ}41'39''\text{S}$, $68^{\circ}21'22''\text{W}$), Argentina.

Site of infection: Cecum and colon.

Etymology: The species name *sanjuanensis* refers to San Juan Province, Argentina, where the host *D. patagonum* was collected.

Type specimens: Holotype male (CRFSJ_P_54A); allotype female (CRFSJ_P_54B); deposited in the Parasitological Collection of the Wildlife Rehabilitation, Environmental Education and Responsible Recreation Center (Parque Faunístico), San Juan Province, Argentina.

Discussion

Currently, two *Aspiculuris* species are known from the Neotropical and Nearctic regions: *A. mexicana* from Oaxaca, Mexico (Lynggaard et al., 2020) and *A. tetraptera* from Venezuela (Hugot, 1980) in the Neotropics; *A. huascaensis* from Hidalgo, Mexico (Falcón-Ordaz et al., 2010) and *A. americana* from Minnesota, Canada (Erickson, 1938) in the Nearctic. In the following study, we identify and describe a new nematode species based on morphological attributes, supported by morphometric measurements. The new nematode species, belonging to the genus *Aspiculuris*, is a parasite of the colon and cecum in *D. patagonum* (Patagonian mara), the most representative endemic mammal of Argentina in the Neotropical region. *Aspiculuris sanjuanensis* sp. nov. differs markedly in size and morphology. In particular, males of *A. sanjuanensis* sp. nov. are three times larger than other *Aspiculuris* species from these regions (see Table 2). Regarding the females of *A. sanjuanensis* sp. nov., they are twice the size of *A. mexicana*, three times the size of *A. americana* and *A. huascaensis*, and nine times the size of *A. tetraptera* (see Table 3).

The new species exhibits a cervical ala that terminates posterior to the bulb-intestine junction, distinguishing it from other species such as *A. tetraptera*, *A. mexicana*, and *A. huascaensis*, in which the cervical ala ends at the midpoint of the oesophageal bulb (see Table 1). *Aspiculuris sanjuanensis* sp. nov. is described for the first time in the mara (*D. patagonum*), an endemic rodent of Argentina belonging to the family Caviidae. Previous descriptions of *A. mexicana*, *A. tetraptera*, *A. huascaensis*, and *A. americana* were based on rodents from the families Muridae and Cricetidae.

Table 1. Comparison of *Aspiculuris sanjuanensis* sp. nov. with the rest of the species from the Neotropical and Nearctic regions.

<i>Aspiculuris</i> spp.	Cervical ala regarding the oesophageal bulb	Number of caudal papillae	Host species	Host family	Country	Region	References
<i>Aspiculuris sanjuanensis</i> sp. nov.	Posterior to the bulb–intestine junction	13	<i>Dolichotis patagonum</i>	Caviidae	San Juan, Argentina	Neotropical	González-Rivas, Castillo & Simoncelli (2025)
<i>Aspiculuris mexicana</i>	Mid-bulb	16	<i>Microtus oaxacensis</i> ; <i>Reithrodontomys mexicanus</i>	Cricetidae	Oaxaca, México	Neotropical	Lynggaard et al. 2020
<i>Aspiculuris tetraptera</i>	Mid-bulb	12	<i>Mastomys natalensis</i>	Muridae	Maracay, Venezuela	Neotropical	Hugot (1980)
<i>Aspiculuris huascaensis</i>	Mid-bulb	12	<i>Mus musculus</i>	Muridae	Hidalgo, México	Nearctic	Falcón-Ordaz et al. (2010)
<i>Aspiculuris americana</i>	Posterior to the bulb–intestine junction	8	<i>Peromyscus maniculatus gracilis</i>	Cricetidae	Minesota, Canada	Nearctic	Erickson (1938)

Table 2. Comparison of morphometric measurements for males of *Aspiculuris sanjuanensis* sp. nov. with species from the Neotropical and Nearctic regions. Measurements in mm.

Morphometric parameter (mm)	<i>Aspiculuris americana</i>	<i>Aspiculuris huascaensis</i>	<i>Aspiculuris tetraptera</i>	<i>Aspiculuris mexicana</i>	<i>Aspiculuris sanjuanensis</i> sp. nov.
Total body length	2.25 – 2.46	2.48	2.7	2.81	6.31
Maximum body width	?	0.096	0.11	0.11	0.192
Cephalic vesicle length	?	0.058	?	0.065	0.0196
Cephalic vesicle width	?	0.065	?	0.07	0.0099
Cervical ala length	0.122	0.208	?	0.27	0.852
Oesophagus length	0.1755	0.175	0.38	0.34	0.808
Bulb length	0.1125	0.097	0.14	0.095	0.251
Bulb width	0.0485	0.051	0.09	0.06	0.161
Distance from anterior end to nerve ring	?	0.080	0.10	0.1	0.259
Tail length	?	?	?	0.19	0.097
Number of caudal papillae	8	12	10+2	16	13
Host species	<i>Peromyscus maniculatus gracilis</i> (Wagner, 1845)	<i>Mus musculus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	<i>Mastomys natalensis</i> (Smith, 1834)	<i>Microtus oaxacensis</i> Goodwin, 1966; <i>Reithrodontomys mexicanus</i> (Saussure, 1860)	<i>Dolichotis patagonum</i>

Table 3. Comparison of morphometric measurements for females of *Aspiculuris sanjuanensis* sp. nov. with species from the Neotropical and Nearctic regions. Measurements in mm.

Morphometric parameter (mm)	<i>Aspiculuris americana</i>	<i>Aspiculuris huascaensis</i>	<i>Aspiculuris tetraptera</i>	<i>Aspiculuris mexicana</i>	<i>Aspiculuris sanjuanensis</i> sp. nov.
Total body length	3.17 – 3.88	3.219	1.2	5.85	9.503
Maximum body width	?	0.12	0.08	0.25	0.393
Cephalic vesicle length	?	0.074	?	0.085	0.0386
Cephalic vesicle width	?	0.076	?	0.125	0.0098
Cervical ala length	120 – 160	0.235	?	0.395	0.965
Esophagus length	0.33	0.322	0.43	0.310	0.931
Bulb length	0.064	0.103	0.16	0.110	0.294
Bulb width	0.043	0.063	0.13	0.090	0.215
Distance from anterior end to nerve ring	217	0.093	0.13	0.145	0.538
Distance from anterior end to vulva	1.25 – 1.45	1.269	1.65	2.15	5.670
Egg length	76 – 83	0.061	0.095	0.074	0.359
Egg width	27 – 35	0.022	0.045	0.039	0.052
Host species	<i>Peromyscus maniculatus gracilis</i>	<i>Mus musculus</i>	<i>Mastomys natalensis</i>	<i>Microtus oaxacensi</i> ; <i>Reithrodontomys mexicanus</i>	<i>Dolichotis patagonum</i>

The description of a new nematode species of the genus *Aspiculuris* in an Argentine-endemic rodent, notable for being the country's second-largest rodent species, enhances our understanding of parasitic nematodes of mammals in both San Juan and Argentina. *Aspiculuris sanjuanensis* sp. nov. is the third *Aspiculuris* species described for the Neotropical region, the first reported in Argentina, and the first recorded in a rodent of the family Caviidae.

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